

Original Article

Public awareness needed to improve the health of food associated allergic diseases

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Abstract

The prevalence of food allergies is becoming significantly greater throughout the world affecting hundreds of millions of persons worldwide. It has posed a serious public health concern worldwide affecting approximately 5% of children under 5 years and 4% of teens and adults, and is showing enhanced prevalence. The patients exhibiting food allergy associated gastrointestinal symptoms like vomiting, diarrhea and bloody stool manifested after intake of specific foods are categorized under a subgroup of food allergy, referred to as gastrointestinal food allergy. The etiology of allergies gastrointestinal diseases are not entirely understood; however, recent evidence indicates that food allergens have an important role in disease pathogenesis in children as well as in adults. Experimental systems have demonstrated that inflammatory responses in allergic diseases are often biphasic, but this has not been well determined in the upper and lower GI tract. The present article signify the public awareness and knowledge to the general population we provided a detailed overview of various factors that are involved in triggering the immune responses that culminate into gastrointestinal allergy that promotes eosinophilic gastrointestinal disorders (EGID).

Introduction

The prevalence of food allergies is becoming significantly greater and the incidence of allergic diseases has continued to raise and pose a major global health concern (Mansueto et al., 2006), (Panel et al., 2010). Evidences suggest that the food allergy is a significant concern among the increasing incidences of majority of allergic diseases (Mansueto et al., 2006), (Panel et al., 2010). Food allergy is a condition where the mucosal immune system starts behaving abnormally against the antigens. It

is an immune-based disease that has posed a serious public health concern worldwide affecting approximately 6% of children under 5 years and 3.7% of teens and adults United States, and is showing enhanced prevalence (Mansueto et al., 2006) (Panel et al., 2010). The most common type of food allergy that is found in adults and older children primarily involves an immune response to inhalant, not ingested allergens that consequently incites a secondary immune response. to a cross-reactive

allergen which is being ingested (Skypala et al., 2011) (Ruiter and Shreffler, 2012). Further, the symptoms of food-related allergic disorders could be mild to severe, and have emerged as a leading cause of anaphylactic reactions leading to approximately 30000 emergency department visits, culminating in about 150-200 deaths each year in the United States (Munoz-Furlong and Weiss, 2009), (Mansueto et al., 2006). Gastrointestinal diseases such as allergic dermatitis (AD), allergic rhinitis (AR), allergic asthma (AA), and allergic gastrointestinal diseases (AGD) are commonly associated with food and aeroallergens.

Food Allergy

The food allergies is significantly increased throughout the world and a number of reports indicates that food allergy affects approximately 4% of adults and about 6% of children less than 3 years of age in the US (Maloney et al., 2006; Sampson, 1997; Sicherer et al., 2004; Sicherer et al., 1999). IgE/mast cell-mediated food allergies are considered serious and life threatening and food-induced anaphylaxis causes approximately 100 deaths/year in the US (Bock et al., 2001; Neugut et al., 2001). These often debilitating disease are characterized by a wide array of manifestations, including elevated levels of IgE, mastocytosis and eosinophilia. In normal condition the immune system of the gastrointestinal mucosa avoids immune reactivity to harmless foreign antigens and promotes oral tolerance (Mansueto et al., 2006) (Breiteneder and Ebner, 2000). Food allergy is a lack of oral tolerance to food that is ingested (Scurlock et al., 2010), (Dubois et al., 2005). It is anticipated that antigen presenting cells which include epithelial cells, dendritic cells, and B cells present the luminal food antigens to naïve T cells that further leads to the formation of Th2 type effector T cell population specific to food

antigen (Scurlock et al., 2010) (Vojdani, 2015). These effector cells then release an array of Th2 cytokines (IL-4, IL-5, IL-9, IL-13 and IL-18) that are primed in the intestinal immune system for triggering food allergy or anaphylactic immune responses upon subsequent exposure to the antigen. (Chehade and Mayer, 2005; Eigenmann and Frossard, 2003) This leads to class-1 food allergy or there is sensitization to certain allergens that are recognized in the course of respiratory exposure, which results in class-2 food allergy (Mansueto et al., 2006) (Dubois et al., 2005). A class-1 food allergy generally results from food proteins that are stable to digestion, which is usually found in infants or children where the immune system is immature. The class-2 food allergy is caused due to sensitization to certain proteins that are encountered in the GI tract and are susceptible to enzymatic degradation leading to IgE production (Mansueto et al., 2006), (Sampson, 2004), (Egger et al., 2006) (Breiteneder and Ebner, 2000). These IgE identify homologous epitopes on food proteins triggering allergic responses. Experimental systems have demonstrated that inflammatory responses in allergic diseases are often biphasic, but this has not been well determined in the upper and lower GI tract. In the early phase responses IgE mast cell-mediated release of histamine, prostaglandin-D2, and cysteinyl-leukotrienes have an important role (Drazen et al., 1996; Holgate et al., 2003); whereas, Th2 cells are thought to promote late phase reactions through the secretion of a number of cytokines like IL-4 and IL-13 (Wills-Karp, 2001). IL-4 promotes Th2 cell differentiation, IgE production, tissue eosinophilia, and, in the case of asthma, morphological changes to the respiratory o activation of epithelium (Brusselle et al., 1994; Rankin et al., 1996). IL-13 is considered to be more of an effector

cytokine in pathogenesis compared to IL-4, as suggested by the finding that a soluble IL-13 receptor blocks many essential features in the experimentally induced disease (Minty et al., 1993; Punnonen et al., 1993; Zurawski and de Vries, 1994a). Although IL-4 and IL-13 have only 25% homology, they share receptor components and have many overlapping functional properties that underlie their role as critical regulators of many of the hallmark features of allergic disease (Kaplan et al., 1996; Takeda et al., 1996). Studies in signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT)6 gene-deficient mice have revealed that IL-13 signaling utilizes the JAK-STAT pathway. The targeted deletion of STAT6 showed impaired development of Th2-associated responses in the GI tract following parasitic infection (Ceponis et al., 2000; Punnonen et al., 1993; Yu et al., 2001). The patients exhibiting food allergy associated gastrointestinal symptoms like vomiting, diarrhea and bloody stool are manifested after intake of specific foods. These patients are categorized under a subgroup of food allergy, referred to as gastrointestinal food allergy. In normal condition the immune system of the gastrointestinal mucosa avoids immune reactivity to harmless foreign antigens and promotes oral tolerance (Mansueto et al., 2006) (Breiteneder and Ebner, 2000). The food allergen-induced gastrointestinal allergy could be either “cell-mediated non-IgE-mediated” or “combined IgE- and cell-mediated” and it encompasses several different clinical entities that include food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome (FPIES), food protein-induced enteropathy, food protein-induced proctocolitis (FPIP), and eosinophilic gastrointestinal disorders (EGID). The gastrointestinal (GI) tract absorbs only about 2% of ingested food antigens (Husby et al., 1985; Husby et al.,

1986) and a number of cells including intestinal epithelial cells, dendritic cells, B cells, and T cells (Hershberg and Mayer, 2000; Strobel and Mowat, 1998) are involved in sampling and processing food antigens in the GI mucosa. It is postulated that antigen presenting cells (epithelial cells, dendritic cells, and B cells) present luminal food antigens to naïve T cells leading to the development of a food antigen-specific Th2 type effector T cell population. These effector cells, through exposure to an array of Th2 cytokines (IL-4, IL-5, IL-9, and IL-13) in the intestinal immune system, are primed for food allergy or anaphylactic reactions upon subsequent antigen exposure (Chehade and Mayer, 2005; Eigenmann and Frossard, 2003). Mast cells and basophils produce IL-5 and IL-13, which induce maturation and activation of eosinophils (Barata et al., 1998; Kung et al., 1995; Sakuishi et al., 2007). Eosinophils, mast cells and basophils along with IgE have an important role in promoting anaphylactic reactions in gastrointestinal allergy.

Eosinophil and Mast cells are the major cell type that promote Allergy

A. Eosinophils. Eosinophils are an important subtype of blood leukocytes and are differentiated from multipotent hematopoietic stem cells in the bone marrow from myeloid lineage myeloblast (Boyce et al., 1995), (Rothenberg, 1998). These eosinophils are multifunctional leukocytes and are involved in vivid innate and adaptive immune responses (Zaidi et al., 2014) (Mishra et al., 2002b; Rothenberg, 1998). Eosinophils home into the gastrointestinal tract in prenatal period, independent to bacterial flora (Mishra et al., 1999). Baseline eosinophil number vary depend upon the geographic condition and seasonal variations (Pascal et al., 1997; Polydorides et al., 2008; Powell et al., 2010).

Eosinophils are reported to initiate inflammatory and adaptive responses because of their interactions with antigen presenting cells and T cells, along with their propensity to synthesize numerous cytokines and a number of mediators. They play a significant role in host defense, regulation of the immune system and in the eradication of parasitic infection (Rothenberg and Hogan, 2006). Eosinophils also has a significant role in the healing and organogenesis before birth (Lee, 2014) Increased level of eosinophilic accumulation in tissue or blood (Figure 1) with marked degranulation is reported in a number of inflammatory diseases (Dutt, 2015; Hogan et al., 2001; Mishra et al., 2001; Mishra et al., 2002a; Mishra et al., 2002b); like asthma, eosinophilic dermatitis, gastroesophageal reflux, celiac disease, inflammatory bowel disease and allergic colitis, food allergy and parasitic infections (Guajardo and Rothenberg, 2003; Hogan et al., 2000; Rothenberg et al., 2001b; Rothenberg et al., 2001c), In normal conditions eosinophils are found in each segment of the GI tract from the stomach to the colon in the lamina propria except the esophagus, Peyers patches, or intra-epithelial locations (DeBrosse et al., 2006; Mishra et al., 2000; Mishra et al., 1999), Further, they are known to have diverse roles in the gastrointestinal tract, which includes excretion of intestinal parasites. Although, it is believed that peristalsis is the major cause of the excretion of intestinal parasites. Despite this eosinophil role in parasite eradication is reported in healthy state and their stimulation promotes the pathogenesis of various allergic gastrointestinal disorders like drug reactions, food allergy, parasitic infection, hypereosinophilic syndromes, allergic colitis, gastroesophageal reflux disease, inflammatory bowel disease. Interleukin, IL-

5 is a well-established differentiation, growth and survival factor for eosinophils (Clutterbuck et al., 1987; Sanderson, 1988; Yamaguchi Y); however, eosinophil lineage commitment, differentiation, effector functions, and the roles in various diseases are under renewed scrutiny (Lee JJ and Lee, 2005; Rosenberg HF, 2001). Yet, it is not clearly understood whether a different subpopulation of eosinophils exists in health and disease. The recruitment of eosinophils in the tissues of IL-5 gene-deficient mice (Mishra et al., 1999) and failed therapeutic trials with humanized anti-IL-5 monoclonal antibodies in asthma and other gastrointestinal disorders (Matthaei KI, 1997; Mishra et al., 1999), indicate that eosinophils may have different subsets. It may be possible that IL-5 independent eosinophil subset also exists in a health and disease state. Which is yet not explored. We earlier reported that baseline eosinophils exist in IL-5 gene-deficient mice (Kaplan et al., 1996); therefore, it is rationale to explore the characteristics of the eosinophil population that exist in IL-5-independent environment. Hence, the researchers and biologist involved in studying eosinophil biology need to explore this possibility and investigate the factors that are responsible for the differentiation and survival of eosinophils in IL-5 gene-deficient mice. The presence of IL-5 independent eosinophil subset may provide a new understanding on eosinophil biology in health and disease.

POTENTIAL ROLE OF EOSINOPHILS IN GASTROINTESTINAL ALLERGY

Eosinophils are recruited in the inflammatory tissue by a complex process which is regulated by various inflammatory cytokines that include IL-3, IL-4, IL-5, GM-CSF and chemokines

which include RANTES, and eotaxins (Rothenberg, 1998). Eosinophil trafficking is selectively regulated by IL-5 and eotaxins that mediate eosinophilic inflammation in allergic diseases (Mishra et al., 2002a; Rothenberg, 1998). Eosinophils home in the lamina propria of the GI tract at baseline, independent of the viable intestinal flora, however their homing is dependent upon eotaxins (Mishra et al., 1999). We have demonstrated that following pulmonary allergen challenge increasing circulating eosinophils do not alter the eosinophil levels in the GI tract indicating that the eosinophil level in the GI tract is regulated by local mechanisms (Mishra et al., 1999). Accumulation of eosinophil in the GI tract is a prominent feature exhibited by numerous disorders like food allergy (Mishra et al., 2001; Rayapudi et al., 2014; Rothenberg et al., 2001a), allergic eosinophilic esophagitis (Mishra et al., 2001), allergic colitis (Sherman and Cox, 1982; Wills-Karp, 2001), allergic gastroenteritis (Katz et al., 1984; Keshavarzian et al., 1985; Mishra et al., 2002b), inflammatory bowel disease (Shinkai et al., 2002), and GERD (Zurawski and de Vries, 1994b) (Minty et al., 1993). Some of these food allergic disorders are highly prevalent and clinically important and have been documented in 2-4% of children and can lead to life threatening conditions (Punnonen et al., 1993) (Takeda et al., 1996) (Kaplan et al., 1996). However, despite of the common observation of eosinophils in the tissue specimens of these patients, the biological and pathological significance of these cells in the GI tract has not been clearly understood. Now, it is generally accepted that eosinophils contribute to the pathogenesis of numerous GI diseases by causing tissue damage through their potent pro-inflammatory and cytotoxic effect (Yu et al., 2001).

EOSINOPHILS MEDIATORS THAT PROMOTES PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE TISSUES

Eosinophils on arrival at the site of inflammatory focus may undergo apoptosis, but if they are activated by IL-3, IL-5, or GM-CSF, they show increased responsiveness to other stimulating agents and survive for prolonged periods (Asquith et al., 2008). Eosinophils can act as antigen-presenting cells, initiating antigen-specific immune response. Eosinophils secretes various cytokines and express major histocompatibility complex class II molecules along with their costimulatory molecules such as CD40, CD28, CD86, B7.1, and B7.2 (Hogan, 2009). Thus they are capable of stimulating lymphocyte proliferation and activation along with polarization of helper Th1 and Th2 cells. Additionally, they can stimulate proinflammatory effects like the up-regulation of GI adhesion systems, tissue remodeling, modulation of leukocyte trafficking, and cellular activation. These effects are mediated by releasing various cytokines including IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, IL-10, IL-12, IL-13, IL-16, IL-18, and TGF- β , TNF- α , GM-CSF, MIP-1 α , chemokines like RANTES and eotaxin-1, eotaxin-3, and lipid mediators like platelet activating factor and leukotriene C4 (Fulkerson and Rothenberg, 2008). Eosinophils also serve as major effector cells, leading to tissue damage and dysfunction by degranulation. Eosinophils undergo degranulation, through at least two distinct mechanisms, defined on the basis of ultrastructural analysis. Eosinophils are commonly undergoing piecemeal degranulation, thus the granular content is released out from the intracellular granules and the empty granules are left intact within the cell (Yu et al., 2001). Eosinophils on

degranulation release toxic granule proteins which involve a crystalloid core composed of major basic protein (MBP), and a matrix composed of eosinophilic cationic protein (ECP), eosinophil peroxidase (EPO), and eosinophil-derived neurotoxin (EDN) along with various lipid mediators (Gleich and Adolphson, 1986) (Hogan, 2009). These cationic proteins have certain common pro-inflammatory properties but they differ in other ways. For example, MBP, EPO, and ECP insert cytotoxic effect on epithelium, at a concentration similar to that found in biological fluids from eosinophilia patients. Additionally, ECP and EDN are members of ribonuclease super-family and possess anti-viral as well as ribonuclease activity (Sampson, 2004; Sicherer et al., 1999). Eosinophil cationic protein act by inserting a voltage insensitive, ion-nonspecific toxic pore into the membranes of the affected cells facilitating the entry of other toxic molecules (Neugut et al., 2001). MBP causes the dysfunctions the vagal muscarinic M2 receptors thus increasing the smooth muscle reactivity (Bock et al., 2001) that also leads to degranulation of mast cells and basophils. Eosinophils also amplify the inflammatory cascade by releasing chemoattractant like RANTES, eotaxin-1, eotaxin-3 and platelet activating factor (PAF) accelerating the recruitment of more eosinophils at the site of inflammatory site (Hogan, 2009). Eosinophils are capable of releasing a number of cytotoxic molecules and lipid mediators that increase the vascular permeability and mucous secretion, and act as potent stimulators of the smooth muscle contraction (Husby et al., 1986). Notably, eosinophils might have a dual function as end-stage effectors as well as immunoregulators in the gastrointestinal tract in health and disease recognized in metastatic progression of prostate cancer.

B. Mast cells in allergic inflammation are

tissue remodeling. Mast cells important effector cells in anaphylaxis and in IgE-associated allergic disease such as atopic asthma, allergic rhinitis and atopic dermatitis (Galli et al., 2005b; Marone et al., 2005; Metcalfe et al., 1997). They are derived from hematopoietic progenitors and differentiate into mature cells locally in all vascularized tissues and can be especially numerous in anatomical sites that are directly exposed to the environment, including the skin, airways and GI tract (Galli et al., 2005b; Kitamura, 1989; Mekori and Metcalfe, 2000; Metcalfe et al., 1997). Several reports indicate that changes in mast cell numbers, as well as local changes in tissue distribution and/or phenotypic characteristics of the cells, are regulated by growth factors such as stem cell growth factor—the main survival and developmental factor for mast cells, IL-3 and the T helper 2 cell associated cytokines IL-4 and IL-9 (Galli et al., 2005a; Kawakami and Galli, 2002; Lu et al., 2006). Mast cells are the source of histamine release and early clinical evidence suggests that anaphylaxis was classically mediated by histamine release in response to antigen cross-linking of IgE bound to FcεR1 (Dybendal et al., 2003; Galli et al., 2005b). However, in a small number of cases, human anaphylaxis has been described in the absence of antigen specific IgE antibodies or detectable levels of mast cell degranulation products such as histamine and tryptase (Dybendal et al., 2003; Golden, 2004; Holgate et al., 2003). Upon stimulation, mast cells rapidly release a number of other secondary mediators including prostaglandin-D2 and leukotrienes (LTC₄, LTD₄ LTE₄), proteoglycans (heparin and chondroitin), platelet-activating factor (PAF), serotonin, proteases (tryptase and chymase) and lipid derived mediators (prostaglandin and leukotrienes (Brandt et al., 2003a; Galli et al., 2005b; Lorentz et al., 1999; Santos et al., 2000; Strait et al., 2002)

These mediators act on target cells to increase vascular permeability, which causes hemoconcentration and depletes intravascular volume resulting in a decrease in vital organ perfusion, cellular inflammation and altering homeostatic GI function and induces the pathophysiological features of disease (Dombrowicz et al., 1993; Kelefiotis and Vakirtzi-Lemonias, 1993; Strait et al., 2002). Recently a number of experimental models were developed to dissect the molecular basis of the end organ effector phase of intestinal anaphylaxis (Brandt et al., 2003b; Li et al., 1999). One such model showed both systemic symptoms and diarrhea with peanut allergen in mice (Li et al., 1999), whereas another model showed diarrhea with no systemic symptoms with OVA allergen in mice (Brandt et al., 2003a). However, both these models showed a critical role for mast cells in intestinal allergic inflammation. Mast cells can provide mediators and cellular functions that have the potential to influence multiple features of the pathology observed at sites of chronic allergic inflammation (Galli et al., 2005a; Galli et al., 2005b; Marone et al., 2005; Marshall and Jawdat, 2004; Marshall et al., 2003; Mekori and Metcalfe, 1999; Metcalfe et al., 1997; Nakae et al., 2005; Williams and Galli, 2000b) At the affected sites, chronic allergic inflammation can be associated with dramatic changes in the extracellular matrix as well as with important alterations in the numbers, structure and function of cells that normally reside there, including epithelial cells, vascular and airway smooth muscle cells, fibroblasts and nerves. In humans, it can be quite difficult to assess the relative importance of the contribution of mast cells to individual examples of chronic allergic inflammation, as opposed to that of the many other cell types that participate in these complex inflammatory disorders. By contrast, work

mice has shown that mast cells can contribute significantly to the development of chronic inflammation (Taube et al., 2004; Williams and Galli, 2000a) and tissue remodeling in a number of experimental systems (Yu et al., 2006). While a number of studies indicated the important role of mast cells in lung and lower GI allergic inflammation, their role in esophageal inflammation has not been explored. Recently two clinical reports indicated that esophageal mast cell numbers increase in EE patients (Blanchard et al., 2006; Kirsch et al., 2007). In this grant application, we will test the role of mast cells in the development of esophageal remodeling and dysfunction.

Role of other inflammatory cells active cytokines and chemokines in the induction of allergic disease

Cytokines and chemokines are categorized as redundant secreted proteins that regulate and determine the nature of immune responses and also regulate immune cell trafficking along with the cellular arrangement of immune organs (Borish and Steinke, 2003). Cytokines primarily promote cellular infiltrate and damage the resident tissue leading to inflammation and are derived from mononuclear phagocytic cells as well as other antigen-presenting cells (Cortes-Vieyra et al., 2012). The antigens on being taken up by APCs, and presented to T-helper lymphocytes lead to cytokine production (Kaiko et al., 2008). Alternatively, monocytes use pattern recognition receptors and recognize stereotypic components of pathogens not found on mammalian cells thus triggering cytokines production by the innate immune system (Borish and Steinke, 2003). The cytokines predominantly produced in patients with food allergy include tumor necrosis factor (TNF), and several interleuk-

in (IL) molecules known as IL-1, IL-3, IL-6, IL-8, IL-12, IL-15, IL-18, and IL-23 (Bartuzi et al., 2000) (Borish and Steinke, 2003). Suggesting that, elevated levels of these cytokines play an important role in the pathogenesis of inflammation. In addition, chemokines are also involved in inflammatory responses, and are produced at the site of infection or as a response to proinflammatory stimulus (Borish and Steinke, 2003). Chemokines are the small (8 to 12 kD) group of molecules that promotes chemotaxis to the various cells like neutrophils, lymphocytes, monocytes, fibroblasts, eosinophils, and keratinocytes. They have also been known to exhibit homeostatic or housekeeping functions involved in adaptive immune responses like lymphocyte trafficking, antigen sampling in secondary lymphoid tissue, hematopoiesis, along with immune surveillance (Rothenberg, 1998). Chemokine overexpression has been reported in numerous inflammatory conditions like inflammatory bowel disease, atherosclerosis, arthritis, microbial infection, asthma, adult respiratory distress syndrome, and malignancy (Katz et al., 1984). Chemokine expression in GI disorders primarily focuses on inflammatory bowel disease; where several cytokines like MCP-1 (Grimm et al., 1996; Reinecker et al., 1995), IL-8 (Chowers et al., 1997), and eotaxin-1 (Garcia-Zepeda et al., 1996; Luster and Rothenberg, 1997) are shown to be present at elevated levels. The primary source of chemokine secretion in these disorders is the intestinal epithelial cells (Reinecker et al., 1995). Indeed, we have earlier shown that transgenic overexpression of eotaxin-1 in enterocytes significantly leads to intestinal eosinophilia (Mishra et al., 2002b). Further the colonic mucosa of coeliac disease patients was reported to have enhanced production of IL-

-8 and MCP-1 on gluten challenge (Chowers et al., 1997; MacDermott et al., 1998).

Role of other inflammatory cells in gastrointestinal allergy

IgE, basophils, and mast cells are the central effector cells involved in the pathogenesis of allergic disease, along with innate and adaptive immunity (Stone et al., 2010). Antigen-specific IgE on being produced subsequently exhibits fixation to FcεRI receptors on mast cells and basophils, thus initiating and propagating immediate hypersensitivity reactions. This leads to release of powerful immunologically active mediators that can either be performed like histamine, cytotoxic proteins, proteases, which could be released within seconds to minutes on being stimulated, or those that are *de novo* synthesized like chemokines, cytokines, and arachidonic acid metabolites that might be released minutes to hours to days after activation (Stone et al., 2010) (Burton and Oettgen, 2011). Mast cells are generated from bone marrow-derived hematopoietic progenitor cells that localize and mature in the vascularized tissues. They are typically long lived and usually reside proximally to epithelia, blood vessels, airways, nerves, mucus-producing glands, and gastrointestinal tract; however they do not recirculate to other vascularized tissues (Okayama and Kawakami, 2006). On being stimulated they trigger a spectrum of compounds that they store in their cytosolic granules, which include biogenic amines like histamine, and serotonin, along with various cytokines, carboxypeptidase, serglycin proteoglycans, and MC-specific proteases like chymase, tryptase (Duelli et al., 2009). Mast cells play central mediators of several IgE-mediated allergic pathologic responses, like passive cutaneous anaphylaxis (PCA) reaction and systemic.

anaphylaxis. Excess of mast cells leads to pathological condition known as mastocytosis, caused by activating mutations in KIT, which notably effects skin, bone marrow, liver, spleen, lymph nodes, and gastrointestinal tract (Stone et al., 2010) (Okayama and Kawakami, 2006). In contrast to mast cells, which reside in tissue, basophils are found circulating in the blood, and constitute <1% of the peripheral blood leukocytes with a short half-life constituting of only a few days (He et al., 2013). Basophils consist of fewer, but larger, granules compared to mast cells however they share several similar features, including FcεRI expression, Th2 cytokines secretion, and release of histamine on being activated. Despite these similarities, basophils have different granular content and the types of eicosanoids produced compared to mast cells and their unique role in allergic conditions and in immune regulation (Siracusa et al., 2013). They express various cytokine receptors including IL-3R, IL-5R, and GM-CSFR; chemokine receptors that include CCR2 and CCR3; prostaglandin receptors CRTH2; complement receptors like CD11b, CD11c, CD35, and CD88 along with immunoglobulin Fc receptors FcεRI and FcγRIIb; and TLRs (Cromheecke et al., 2014). Similar to mast cells, mediators that are produced by basophils are also divided into preformed mediators, which prominently includes histamine, newly synthesized lipid mediators, and cytokines/chemokines (Siracusa et al., 2013). It has been shown that murine models that were immunized with protease allergen, ovalbumin, or helminth infection depicted a direct role for basophils in antigen presentation leading to Th2 response induction, along with MHC class II molecules expression and IL-4 production (Teitelbaum et al., 2002) (Straumann et al., 2001) mast cells also participate in gastrointestinal disease pathogenesis by generating a number of proinflammatory mediators that activate eosinophils and promote tissue remodeling (Mueller et al., 2006;

;Niranjan et al., 2013). A recent report indicates that both eosinophils and mast cells correlate with disease severity in human (Blanchard et al., 2006). Studies with a murine model shows that mast cells are critical in promoting muscle cell hyperplasia and hypertrophy in experimental EoE (Niranjan et al., 2013). Furthermore, most recently elevated basophil levels have been shown in human allergic eosinophilic esophagitis and basophil depletion in experimental setup ameliorated the disease (Noti et al., 2013). Taken together, this suggests that mast cells and basophils contribute to the gastrointestinal disorders and promote EGID pathogenesis. In addition, new data emerging indicates that iNKT cells are also critical in health and disease and its activation, releases a number of inflammatory Th1, Th2 and Th17 cytokines including IFN-γ, IL-4 (Straumann et al., 2001; Teitelbaum et al., 2002), IL-5 and IL-13 (Akbari, 2006; Sakuishi et al., 2007; Wilson and Delovitch, 2003). Previously, iNKT cells were implicated in the induction of number of allergic diseases including (Rajavelu et al., 2012; Teitelbaum et al., 2002) (Iwamura and Nakayama, 2007; Meyer et al., 2007; Straumann et al., 2001) and recently, it was demonstrated that iNKT cell functionally-deficient mice protected from aeroallergen as well as food allergen (peanut and *Aspergillus*) induced experimental eosinophilic esophagitis (Rayapudi et al., 2014).

CONCLUSION

Our review concludes that food allergy is critical in promoting gastrointestinal allergy. In response to food allergy a number of inflammatory cells such as eosinophils, mast cells, and basophils accumulate in GI tract with the help of their specific cytokines and chemokines and trigger an array of immune responses. Herein, we have discussed the eosinophil biology, food allergy and the factors

influence in promoting the pathogenesis of gastrointestinal allergy. We provided a detailed significance of food allergy including the activation of IgE, eosinophils, mast cells and basophils in promoting tissue inflammation and remodeling during the development of pathogenesis culminating in gastrointestinal allergy. Additionally, a number of evidences are provided regarding the prominent role of various inflammatory cells active cytokines, chemokines in the development of EGID. Hence, the current review provided in depth summarized understanding on the different factors involved in promoting food allergen-induced gastrointestinal diseases. The schematic figure 1 summarizes the pathway that may be operational in promoting food allergen-induced gastrointestinal diseases

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